

Angelo Leogrando^{1}*

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

^oLUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

Investment as a Percentage of GDP in Europe

Between 2000 and 2021 they decreased by 6.8%

It is an indicator that measures the value of investment in terms of GDP as a percentage of GDP. The indicator shows the share of GDP used for gross investment. Both business investment, household investment and public sector investment are considered.

Ranking of countries by value of investment as a percentage of GDP in Europe. Estonia ranks first in value of investments as a percentage of GDP with an amount of 28.86%, followed by Hungary with an amount of 27.4% and Austria with a value of 26.48%. In the middle of the table are Latvia with an amount of 22.26%, followed by Malta with an amount of 22.05% and Germany with an amount of 21.76%. In the last places are Poland with an amount of 17.04%, followed by Luxembourg with an amount of 16.55% and Greece with an amount of 13.27%.

Ranking of countries by the value of the percentage change in investment as a percentage of GDP between 2000 and 2021. Norway ranks first in the value of the percentage change in investment as a percentage of GDP with an amount of 16.87% equal to an amount of 3.34 units, followed by Sweden with a value of 14.20% equal to 3.16 units, and by France with a value of 12.69% equal to an amount of 2.73 units. In third place is France with a growth of 12.69% equal to an amount of 2.73 units. In the middle of the table is Italy with an amount of -1.54% equal to an amount of -0.32 units, followed by Ireland with a value of -1.98% equal to -0.47 units, followed by from Malta with a value of -2.86% equal to an amount of -0.65 units. The ranking is closed by Portugal with an amount of -27.50% equal to an amount of -7.7 units, followed by Poland with a value of -28.07% equal to -6.65 units, followed by Greece with a value of -46.14% equal to an amount of -11.37 units. Overall, between 2000 and 2021, the value of investments as a percentage of GDP decreased by an amount equal to 6.8%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. A clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient is presented below. An optimal value is identified with k=3. The three clusters are identified below, namely:

- Cluster 1: Estonia, Czechia, Latvia;
- Cluster 2: Sweden, Austria, Finland, Belgium, Hungary, Norway, France, Slovakia, Spain, Slovenia, Ireland, Croatia;
- Cluster 3: Italy, Luxembourg, Poland, Greece, Cyprus, Netherlands, Portugal, Germany, Malta, Denmark, Lithuania.

From the point of view of the median, the following ordering of the clusters results: C1=25.71>C2=23.15>19.67. From a geographical point of view, the Baltic countries are in the lead, followed by the countries of central-northern Europe and the countries of southern Europe, to which are added, however, also the Netherlands, Germany, and Poland.

Network analysis using the Euclidean distance. A network analysis with Euclidean distance is presented below. A single complex network structure is detected, i.e.:

¹Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrando.cultore@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

- Sweden has a connection with Belgium with a value of 0.73 units, and with Finland with a value equal to 0.85 units;
- Finland has a connection with Sweden in the amount of 0.85 units, with France in the amount of 0.82 units and with Belgium in the amount of 0.68 units;
- France has a connection with Finland for the amount of 0.82 units and with Belgium for the amount of 0.69 units;
- Belgium has a connection with Sweden worth 0.73 units, with France worth 0.69 units and with Finland worth 0.68 units.

Conclusion. The value of investments as a percentage of GDP decreased between 2000 and 2021 by an amount equal to 6.8%. The average value of investments as a percentage of GDP peaked in 2007, reaching a value of 25.47%. However, since 2008 it has decreased to a low of 18.84% in 2013. From 2013 onwards the average value of investments as a percentage of GDP has grown to a value of 22.87% in 2019. From 2019 onwards, the value of investments as a percentage of GDP decreased slightly from an amount of 22.87% to a value of 21.97%. It therefore follows that the 2007 crisis and the Covid 19 crisis had a very negative impact in reducing the value of investments as a percentage of GDP in Europe. However, there are some countries for which the value of investment as a percentage of GDP has decreased significantly as for example in the case of Greece which has halved the value of investment. Significant reductions in terms of investment have also occurred in the Netherlands, Germany, and Spain. The reduction in investment as a percentage of GDP in Europe is a serious matter. The European industrial system tends to be uncompetitive with respect to the USA and Asian countries. Furthermore, technology investments in Europe are less structured than in the USA. From this emerges the picture of a weakened Europe in the investment structure significantly affected by the crises of 2007 and by the crisis connected to the Covid 19 pandemic. Furthermore, the reduction of investments in key countries such as for example Germany and the Netherlands tends to highlight an element crisis that could become very worrying especially in connection with the current inflation and with the friction of the international markets between the USA and China.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Media del Valore degli Investimenti in Percentuale del PIL

C1>C2>C3

